

BB-2208

Human Resource Management

Case Study Analysis — Digital HRM

Agrowmetro Company

Nur Sabrina binti Zaini

19B8510

11th November 2020

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Introduction

Agriculture is the art and science of cultivating the soil, growing crops and raising livestock according to National Geographic (2011). Agriculture Entrepreneurs or Agripreneurs do not differ from the basic traits of Entrepreneurs, who has the ability to transform their ideas into business. However, their main focus of business is on agriculture.

Agriculture was once an important economic activity in Brunei but has declined in importance since the discovery of oil in 1929. In 1947, more than 50 percent of the population are employed in agriculture but decreased to 10 percent in 1971.

Agrowmetro Company is a partnership founded by four inspiring youths. Their company specializes in the hydroponic system which is a modern method for cultivating vegetables. Their company's mission is to revamp and transform farming technology by making advancements suitable to Brunei. Their company's vision is to inspire the young generation to be involved in agriculture and encourage farming enthusiasts to be able to grow their own crops despite limited time and space.

Agrowmetro offers three different types of hydroponics:

- Mini hydroponic and Mobile hydroponic with four storeys and can cultivate 44 crops at any given time
- Vertical hydroponic with 30 plant holes
- Fruit hydroponic with 36 plant holes to grow fruits

Agrowmetro has sold about 100 hydroponics system to date and are still receiving a number of orders for more to be completed.

Problem Statement

Agrowmetro lacks in human resources and limits in finances. Initially, they considered hiring some of their friends but they were unable to pay their salary sufficiently as they were not making enough income. Income received were split among them and the excess were used to purchase raw materials and tools required for their company. It is a major problem as they are a small company comprising of four students without a human resource manager, making it difficult to form a team. Although their company received financial startup from their supervisor, it was only a loan which was then repaid with the income received from the first batch of hydroponic sets that they sold. It is difficult for them to receive funds because companies tend to meticulously consider on who they decide to invest on.

Human resources department is crucial for a company's success, from small businesses to large corporations. They are not only required to perform during payroll processing and handling enrollments when necessary, but also helps to develop a company's strategy and handles the organisation's employee-centered activities. Firstly, with a proper human resource department, the company will be able to control their budget. They will curate methods to cut costs associated with the workforce management, eventually reducing excessive expenses and help the company save more profit in the long run. Secondly, the human resource department is responsible for ensuring employee satisfaction of their supervisors, job, and related duties. Their satisfaction can be measured by the distribution of surveys, overseeing focus groups and implementing interviews to determine how the company can improve in relation to its employees. Thirdly, human resource managers are in charge in conducting training and development towards the company's employees to ensure that they perform their duties efficiently. This will be done by identifying their skills and qualification to match their tasks. Fourthly, human resource department helps to resolve any conflicts within the workplace, in

regards to their job, managers or co-workers. A human resource manager is trained to handle relations between employees, eventually identifying and resolving the conflicts to ensure a positive working environment. Lastly, the human resource department is responsible for the development of performance management systems. This is used to measure employee performance, to assess whether or not they are suitable in the position according to their expertise and skills (Human Resource MBA, n.d.).

In a small business, working capital measures the company's current assets minus their current liabilities. This capital reflects the company's effectiveness and short-term financial stability. To function effectively, small business owners require more positive working capital. Therefore, a shortage of working capital poses several drawbacks. Firstly, it can be challenging for a small business that needs adequate working capital to draw investors. Working capital indicates to investors that a business has the potential to repay its loan. The inability to attract investors can affect the ability of a business to buy their acquired resources. Secondly, working capital evaluates the ability of a business to convert short-term assets into profit. Lack of working capital can endanger the ability of a business to finance its day-to-day operations such as the acquisition of inventory and requirements for equipment. If a business loses a majority of its inventory under unexpected circumstances, lack of working capital may be impossible to substitute. Thirdly, positive working capital enables small businesses to expand. A lack of working capital inhibits a business from gaining what it needs to establish. Lastly, in order to remain sustainable, small businesses struggling to maintain a positive working environment must take action to improve the situation. This can be done by focusing on collecting cash payments to increase the amount of working capital. If assets are not converted into cash, a business can experience cash flow issues. Selling long-term assets in change for cash is among the strategies to boost working capital (Johnson, n.d.).

Human resources are a common issue and a tough challenge for small business owners to overcome. Budget is a main factor in the lack of human resources which makes them unable to hire a human resource specialist as business owners are often dealing with it all by themselves. Therefore, it is vital for a small business to address the issues faced to appropriately decide on the solution. They need to consider on how to improve their human resources and overcome their shortage of funds.

Case Analysis

Agrowmetro proves to not have implemented any kind of human resource management as they rely on themselves to run the company without a human resource manager. The information technology (IT) possibilities for human resource management (HRM) are endless because all human resource practices can easily be done and supported by IT. Almost every organisation can benefit from implementing a personalized HRM software, whether coming from a small business to as big as multinational corporation. When a business expands, it often becomes difficult to handle the human resources of an organisation as the number of employees increases. For small businesses today, there are many variations of human resource software. Strategic management, personnel planning, and employment, training and development, policy formulation, etc. are the main functions of human resources. It is beneficial for a business to have a comprehensive HRM system to cover daily human resource duties and related activities.

According to Knowarth Technologies (2019), the benefits of using a Human Resource Management System includes:

Streamlines processes and workflows — Organisations can establish a hierarchy with a HRM system. User roles and permissions are clearly defined to ensure that every user knows their position which helps to rationalize the internal processes.

Reduces paperwork — HRM system reduces a lot of paperwork, helps standardize procedures such as job records, personal information, certifications, qualifications, and compensation information relevant to employee information. It also saves time by collecting and keeping all the business data in one place. Through encryption, HRM system also helps to secure sensitive information from both hackers and unauthorized users.

Payroll system — By protecting information with password authorization and storing information, HRM system provides a more convenient way to process paychecks. This can be easily utilized to process the payments for travel, salary, incentives, and several other employee expenses.

On-boarding and employee self-service — Employees will be able to maintain their personal as well as professional details through an employee self service portal. An employee can monitor their leaves, holiday schedule, leaves of other employees with the access to HRM system. This system enables employees to edit or add information either from home or from a client location.

Employee efficiency — Employees are able to identify their Key Performance Index (KPI) and determine how effectively resources work and achieve their business goals through a HRM system. Constant performance related data analysis is likely to have a positive effect on employee performance, and past data may also provide strategic insights into salaries, incentives, and preparation for future professional objectives.

A healthy working capital is vital for every business to survive. The benefits of a positive working capital according to My Company Funding, includes reserves to get through rough patches, ability to expand business, acquisition of revenue generating assets, and potential to buy out a silent or ineffective partner. A sufficient amount of working capital guarantees that the business will flow without interruption. It ensures that the business, in the short-term, will

not run out of cash. Purchasing inventory or raw materials and meeting payroll are non-negotiable operating costs, but earning enough profit helps to retain the company's integrity. To buy resources in bulk requires sufficient capital to be eligible for discounts, therefore, when sales increase, it can be easily scaled up provided with the available resources.

Alternative Solutions

A possible solution for Agrowmetro is to consider hiring a human resource specialist. It does not necessarily have to be a team, but sufficient enough for a start. Agrowmetro should no longer overlook the importance of human resources, even though they are a small business. These issues cannot be handled by a director, head manager, marketing manager or resident seedling expert because each position has their own job scope, and they all have their own issues to deal with. A human resource manager will be able to help expand their business, and they will be able to hire new employees to help market their business.

Uber, in 2014, when it had already progressed to over 500 employees, finally hired its first human resource specialist. Although Uber is not cash-strapped, its management waited until it had hundreds of employees before recruiting a human resource specialist because it treated human resource like many new businesses do, in an atmosphere of "growth at all costs." Despite Uber expanding its human resource department, recruiting roles were still prioritized by management over legal compliance, ethics, diversity, and other significant human resource functions. Tasks such as combating sexual assault, ensuring equal pay, and measuring results objectively were not among the priorities of human resource. These issues led to its CEO, Travis Kalanick, resigning (Lennon, n.d.).

In order to develop workplace expectations, supervise hiring and promotions, and ensure ethical conduct, businesses without structured human resource departments rely on their management teams. Therefore, the whole business will suffer if management runs into trouble and there is no human resource department who is willing to step in to resolve the issue.

Running a business, whether small business or multinational companies, entails a large number of responsibilities and issues for owners, with the most common problem related to finance. Lack of enough capital to hold the company to keep running, is one of the key causes for small business failure. Approximately 44 percent of small businesses operate for at least four years, according to Small Business Association. Common grounds for business closure as cited by All Business includes bad capital structure, over spending, and lack of reserve funds.

Agrowmetro should consider reviewing, revamping, researching, and rewriting their business plan to resolve financial problems. The company can consider obtaining loans and grants explicitly tailored to help support existing businesses. The owner of the company would be permitted to refinance their business debt by certain lenders. Financial support is offered by some localities and private community organisations to established small business that agree to attend training seminars. Venture capitalists and angel investors prefer to take greater chances and will be able to help small business owners maintain operations with the financing they want as long as the business owner can prove their business plan's viability.

Recommendations

Management of the most important assets in an organisation, its employees, is the role of a human resource department in every company. It is not unusual for businesses to function without one, however, it raises their likelihood of business failure. If Agrowmetro is unable to

hire a human resource specialist, appoint one in the established company to be a human resource manager. They can also consider getting proper training and education so that they have the qualifications and be confident in taking on human resource duties. They should also implement a HRM system to ensure a consistent approach in their daily activities. Online programmes are offered for businesses to monitor, control, and report on routine regarding human resource matters such as holiday, sick leave, and performance review. These tools are valuable for businesses that does not have a human resource department or specialist. The most important factor is that an online system reduces uncertainty on whether or not an employee's holiday is approved, whether or not they are on leave, etc. and reduces unnecessary paperwork.

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